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Determining critical parameters of hydrogen reduction treatment of low copper-containing primary slags

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 958307

European project **HARARE**

Molten state reduction of copper slag together with Aurubis AG and Linde AG

Motivation

- Copper slag
 - Generation of 2.2 t slag per t primary copper
 - 24 mio.t copper production per year (worldwide)
 - ~ 1 wt. % copper in slag (often < 1 wt.% in ore)
 - ~ 2 % of smelter copper input
- Hazard elements in ores
 - ~ 2 wt.% harmful elements (increasing)
 - Pb, Zn, As, Mo
 - Issues in slag applications
- What's it all for?
 - Increasing demand of CO₂ neutral and social fair produced metals

Potential future TC ranges for copper concentrate

Flow sheet of process

Advantage of hydrogen

- ❑ Fast kinetics
- ❑ Easy adjustable reduction potential

Disadvantages

- ❖ Low spec. reduction amount
- ❖ Iron phase with high melting point

Lab scale setup

- Resistant heated furnace
- Refractory lining
- Ceramic lance
- Temperature 1300 °C
- 1 500 g input material
- < 2 l/min volume flow (4,66/min melt volume)
- 15 – 90 vol. % H₂

	Fe	Si	Cu	Pb	Zn	Ca	Al	Ni & Sn	Rest
Slag 1	38.8	15.3	0.9	0.3	1.2	1.7	2.4	< 0.1	39.4
Slag 2	37.6	15.8	2.0	0.7	1.0	1.8	2.2	< 0.2	38.7

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Reduction of copper

- Efficiency stays equal
 - ☐ Hydrogen entering the melt will react fast
 - ☐ No diffusion problem at high turbulence
- How to classify kinetic increase?

Calculation of reaction order

- Linear shape seems to be first order
- Graphic progression of k
 - First order reaction

First-order reaction: Doubling the concentration, also doubling rate constant

➤ Stays first order for high concentrations

Conc.	15 %	30 %	45 %	90 %
k	0,006	0,012	0,020	0,038
factor	-	x2	-	x2

$$c = a \cdot \exp^{-k}$$

Influence of turbulence

- Trials with pure hydrogen
- Increasing rate constant with turbulence
 - Increase of 2,2
- Influencing parameter

Influence of concentration

Higher Cu-conc leads to:

- Increasing influence of turbulence
- Higher H₂ yield

	<1 wt.% Cu	<2 wt.% Cu
1 l/min	-0,0177	-0,0206
2 l/min	-0,0181	-0,0255
	[wt.% Cu/(l H ₂ *kg slag)]	

▲ 1 l/min, 2 wt.% Cu

● 2 l/min, 2 wt.% Cu

▲ 1 l/min, 1 wt.% Cu

● 2 l/min, 1 wt.% Cu

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Closer look on slag phase

- 1 wt.% Cu slag as input
- Main impurities could be decreased
 - $\sum \text{As, Sb} < 0,05 \text{ wt.}\%$
- Copper recovery 63 %
- Metal phase with $< 20 \text{ wt.}\%$ Fe
- ❖ Influence of $\text{H}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ interesting

Conclusion and Outlook

- Influence on reaction
 - ❑ Vol.% H₂, turbulence, wt.% Cu
 - ❑ Fast reaction, mass transfer important
 - ❑ Influences decrease with wt.% Cu
- Slag phase cleaned from hazardous elements
- 63 % of copper could be recovered
- Highly turbulent reactor with high H₂-conc.

Outlook

- Pilot scale tests with up to 500 kg slag
- Investigation on iron reduction (2nd reduction step)
- H₂/H₂O ratio with project partner

THANK YOU

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